

A Prospective Study of Cytological and Histopathological Spectrum of Thyroid Lesions at Tertiary Care Hospital at Jaipur

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Abstract:

Background: The thyroid gland, a key endocrine organ, produces hormones like thyroxine (T4), triiodothyronine (T3), and calcitonin. Thyroid disorders, prevalent worldwide, vary by age, sex, diet, environment, and geography. Commonly encountered in hospitals, these disorders include developmental, inflammatory, hyperplastic, and neoplastic lesions, with goiter being a significant global health issue. Most thyroid enlargements are non-neoplastic, with only 5-10% being malignant. Distinguishing between benign and malignant nodules based solely on clinical features is challenging, making Fine Needle Aspiration Cytology (FNAC) crucial for accurate diagnosis.

Results: This study included 70 cases with ages ranging from 16 to 68 years, averaging 41.9 years. Of these, 70.0% were under 50 years old. The gender distribution was predominantly female (85.7%). Lesion distribution showed diffuse lesions as the most common type, primarily affecting females. Cytological examination revealed goitre as the most frequent finding, followed by benign thyroid disease and thyroiditis. Histopathological correlation showed thyroid adenoma as the most prevalent diagnosis. The majority of cases (90.0%) fell into Bethesda Category II (benign). The study found a strong correlation between cytological and histological diagnoses, with 97.8% accuracy for non-neoplastic lesions and 100% accuracy for neoplastic lesions. Statistical analysis showed a sensitivity of 85.7%, specificity of 100%, PPV of 100%, and NPV of 97.7%.

Conclusion: Cytological and histological evaluations are highlighted as essential tools in distinguishing between benign and malignant lesions. While the study acknowledges limitations such as a small sample size and single-institution design, its comprehensive data collection and analysis provide a strong foundation for understanding thyroid cases.

Keywords: Thyroid Gland, FNAC, Histopathology, Papillary Carcinoma.

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Introduction

Thyroid gland is a butterfly shaped endocrine gland situated in the anterior aspect of root of the neck, consists of two bulky lateral lobes connected by a relatively thin isthmus. Thyroid produces several hormones such as thyroxine (T4), triiodothyronine (T3) and calcitonin. Disorders of thyroid comprise a group of commonly encountered endocrinological disease. It is most prevalent in mountainous areas but also occurs in non-mountainous areas remote from sea. [1]

The prevalence and pattern of these thyroid diseases in a given community is variable depending on various factors including age, sex, dietary, environmental factors and geographical patterns. Thyroid diseases are among the commonly encountered diseases in any hospital.

They include a vast array of developmental, inflammatory, hyperplastic and neoplastic lesions. Goiter is a major health concern in many parts of the world. [2] Thyroid diseases are very important because the majority of them can be treated with medication or surgery. [3] When making a diagnosis solely on the basis of a clinical evaluation, it can often be difficult.

Therefore, it is important to emphasize both clinical evaluation and Fine Needle Aspiration Cytology (FNAC) investigation of such lesions in order to aid in accurate diagnosis. Thyroid gland enlargement is a common presentation in the general population but all thyroid enlargements do not require surgery. Thyroid nodules are common but thyroid cancer is uncommon. [4] Clinical

presentation is most commonly for hypothyroidism, goitres and infrequently for hyperthyroidism. Thyroid enlargements may be diffuse or nodular, at times causing obvious physiological changes. Nodular lesions comprise those disorders that produce a clinical nodule and consist of non-neoplastic hyperplasia as well as benign and malignant tumors. Majority of thyroid lesions are non-neoplastic and 5%-10% are malignant. Clinical features alone cannot distinguish between benign and malignant nodules. [5]

The current standard of care for thyroid nodule cytology is fine-needle aspiration. Following World War II, reports in medical journals began to surface indicating that between 20% and 30% of patients with surgically removed thyroid nodules would eventually develop thyroid cancer. 4,5 Palpable thyroid nodules affect 4% to 7% of adults in the general population, while subclinical (nonpalpable) nodules affect up to 70% of people. Between 90% and 95% of these thyroid nodules are benign. [6]

Incidence of thyroid malignancy is quite low, 1 in 20 clinically identified nodules turn out to be malignant, thus thyroid Fine needle aspiration cytology (FNAC) helps in reducing the rate of surgery for benign thyroid diseases. Fine-needle aspiration (FNA) is currently regarded as the first choice during workup for thyroid nodules due to the critical need for a trustworthy preoperative diagnosis. N. Soderstrom first described fine-needle aspiration cytology of the thyroid in 1952, and it has been widely accessible since the 1970s. [7]

Fine needle aspiration cytology (FNAC) is now a well-established, first line, simple and quick screening test as well as the diagnostic tool for surgical and nonsurgical goiters. It is a very useful modality to decide on the patient's requiring surgery from those who need not be operated. [8] The present study was done to Study cytological and Histopathological spectrum of thyroid lesions and to determine the sensitivity and specificity of FNAC in the diagnosis of thyroid lesions.

Material and Methods

This is a hospital based observational cross-sectional study conducted at RUHS-CMS, with attached Jaipuria hospital, Jaipur for the period of 18 months. Patients attending the hospital OPD with thyroid lesion constituted the study material according to inclusion and exclusion criteria.

Inclusion Criteria:

- Palpable and non-palpable nodules of thyroid
- Patients who were willing to participate in the study.
- All FNAC smears should have adequate cellularity.
- Seven days before the test, the patient has to stop taking aspirin or other blood thinners.

Exclusion Criteria:

- Unsuitable specimen if, consist of blood or if cellular material is absent or cellular material is insufficient.
- Poorly preserved specimen in which material is adequate but the morphology is not discernible.
- All toxic goiters which are confirmed by clinical and serological diagnosis.
- Vascular lesion

Sampling Technique: Convenience sampling, study participants are selected based on availability and willingness to participate in the survey. Cases were selected from OPD of RUHS-CMS attached Jaipuria hospital.

Study Procedure (Methodology): The procedure was explained to the patient in complete details and after explanation, informed and valid and written consent was taken. All cytological and biopsy specimens collected as per inclusion criteria and cytological specimens were subjected to the fixation with 95% ethyl alcohol, smear are prepared and biopsy specimen fixed with 10 % formalin, grossing, tissue processing, staining with Harris haematoxylin and eosin stain. Microscopic evaluation was done of each specimen.

Results:

In the present study, we included 70 cases according to the inclusion and exclusion criteria. The ages ranged from 16 to 68 years with the average age of 41.9 years \pm 13.86 years, indicating that most of the cases were in their early forties. Out of 70 cases, 49 (70.0%) were under 50 years, while 21 (30.0%) were 50 years or older and the difference of distribution was statistically significant (p-value = 0.001). [Graph 1] Out of 70 cases, 60 (85.7%) were female, and 10 (14.3%) were male. [Graph 2]

Table no 1 presents the gender distribution within two age groups. The p-value of 0.456 indicates no statistically significant difference in gender distribution between the two age groups.

Graph 1: Age Group Category among Study Cases

Graph 2: Gender Wise Distribution of Cases

The table no 2 categorizes lesions by type and age group, there were 49 cases (70.0%) under 50 years and 21 cases (30.0%) 50 years or older (p-value = 0.914) Diffuse lesions were the most common with 16 cases, followed by diffuse nodular with 9 cases.

Table 1: Distribution of Study Cases by Age Group and Gender

Age Group	Female	Male	Total	p-Value
< 50 Years	41 (83.7%)	8 (16.3%)	49 (100.0%)	0.456
>= 50 Years	19 (90.5%)	2 (9.5%)	21 (100.0%)	
Total	60 (85.7%)	10 (14.3%)	70 (100.0%)	

Table 2: Distribution of Type of Lesion among Age Group Categories

Type of Lesion	< 50 Years Count (%)	≥ 50 Years Count (%)	Total Count (%)	p - Value
Cystic	3 (60.0%)	2 (40.0%)	5 (100.0%)	0.914
Diffuse	11 (68.8%)	5 (31.3%)	16 (100.0%)	
Diffuse Nodular	7 (77.8%)	2 (22.2%)	9 (100.0%)	
Multinodular	2 (100.0%)	0 (0.0%)	2 (100.0%)	
Nodular	25 (67.6%)	12 (32.4%)	37 (100.0%)	
Nodulocystic	1 (100.0%)	0 (0.0%)	1 (100.0%)	
Total	49 (70.0%)	21 (30.0%)	70 (100.0%)	

Among the cystic lesions, 4 cases (80%) were female, and 1 case (20%) was male. Diffuse lesions were exclusively observed in females (16 cases,

100%). Diffuse nodular lesions affected 6 females (66.7%) and 3 males (33.3%). Multinodular and nodulocystic lesions were found only in females,

with 2 and 1 cases, respectively (100% each). Nodular lesions were more common in females, with 31 cases (83.8%), compared to 6 cases in

males (16.2%). There was no statistically significant difference in lesion distribution by gender ($X^2 = 6.079$, $df = 5$; $p = 0.299$). [Graph 3]

Graph 3: Distribution of Type of Lesion among Gender Group

Table 3: Distribution of Cytological Findings among Study Sample

Cytology Findings	Frequency	Percent
Thyroiditis (Lymphocytic/Autoimmune –Thyroiditis)	8	11.5
Benign Thyroid Disease	20	28.7
Goiter	33	47.1
Thyroid Adenoma	2	2.8
Follicular Lesion of Undetermined Significance (FLUS)	1	1.4
Papillary Carcinoma of Thyroid	6	8.5
Total	70	100.0

On cytological examination, the most common finding was Goitre, observed in 33 cases (47.1%), followed by Benign Thyroid Disease, identified in 20 cases (28.7%).

Thyroiditis, specifically lymphocytic or autoimmune thyroiditis, was found in 8 cases

(11.5%). Papillary Carcinoma of the Thyroid was present in 6 cases (8.5%). Less common findings included Thyroid Adenoma, noted in 2 cases (2.8%), and Follicular Lesion of Undetermined Significance (FLUS), found in just 1 case (1.4%). [Table 3]

Table 4: Distribution of Histological Findings among Study Cases

Histological Findings	Frequency	Percent
Colloid Cyst	5	9.8
Thyroiditis	8	15.6
Goiter		
I. Colloid Goiter	10	19.6
II. Multinodular Goiter	7	13.7
Thyroid Adenoma	14	27.4
Papillary Carcinoma	6	11.7
Follicular Carcinoma	1	1.9
Total	51	100.0

Note: Histology reports of 19 cases out of 70 not available at the time of final data analysis

In total, histopathological correlation was available in 51 cases out of the 70 patients with FNAC smears.

The most common finding was thyroid adenoma, with 14 cases (27.4%), followed by colloid goiter, present in 10 cases (19.6%), and thyroiditis, found in 8 cases (15.6%). Colloid cysts and papillary carcinoma were less prevalent, with 5 (9.8%) and 6 (11.7%) cases respectively. Multinodular goiter was identified in 7 cases, making up 13.7% of the total, while the least condition observed was follicular carcinoma, with only one case (1.9%). [Table 4] On studying the distribution of Bethesda Categories among a study sample of 70 cases, the

majority of cases fall into Bethesda Category II, which is characterized by benign findings. Specifically, 63 out of 70 cases, or 90.0%, are classified as Category II. Only 1 case (1.4%) is categorized under Bethesda Category III, which typically indicates atypical cells that may warrant further investigation. Meanwhile, 6 cases (8.6%) fall into Bethesda Category VI, which denotes malignant findings. [Graph 4]

This distribution suggests that while the majority of cases were benign, there were a small number of cases with either atypical or malignant results that could require additional diagnostic or therapeutic measures.

Graph 4: Distribution of Bethesda Category among Study Sample

In the present study, for females under 50, all 40 cases (71.9% of this group) are classified as Bethesda Category II (benign), with no cases in the suspicious or malignant categories.

In females aged 50 and older, 16 cases (28.1%) are benign, 1 case (0%) is suspicious, and 3 cases (100% of malignancies) are malignant, indicating a rise in suspicious and malignant findings with age. For males, those under 50 have 6 cases (85.7%) in

Bethesda Category II and 2 cases (66.7%) in Category VI, with no suspicious cases. Males 50 and older show 1 benign case (14.3%) and 1 malignant case (33.3%).

Overall, younger individuals mostly have benign findings, while older individuals show more suspicious and malignant lesions, highlighting the need for careful monitoring in older patients. [Graph 5]

Graph 5: Distribution of Bethesda Category Cases in Age Group by Gender

Table 5: Comparison of Cytology and Histology Report in Study Sample

Cytological Diagnosis	Histological Diagnosis		Total
	Neoplastic	Non-Neoplastic	
Neoplastic	6 (100.0%)	0 (0.0%)	6 (100.0%)
Non-Neoplastic	1 (2.2%)	44 (97.8%)	45 (100.0%)
Total	7 (13.7%)	44 (86.3%)	51 (100.0%)

On cross-tabulation of cytological and histological diagnosis, focusing on whether the findings were neoplastic or non-neoplastic. Among the cases with a cytological diagnosis of neoplastic, all 6 cases (100%) were confirmed as neoplastic by histology.

This indicates a strong correlation between cytological and histological diagnoses in identifying neoplastic conditions. For cases with a cytological diagnosis of non-neoplastic, 44 out of 45 cases (97.8%) were confirmed as non-neoplastic by histology, while only 1 case (2.2%) was found to be neoplastic upon histological examination (Benign Thyroid disease by cytology v/s Papillary

Carcinoma of thyroid by Histology). This suggests a high degree of accuracy for non-neoplastic cytological diagnoses. Overall, the total distribution of histological diagnoses reveals that 13.7% of the cases were neoplastic, while 86.3% were non-neoplastic. [Table 5]

In present study we observed the accuracy of 97.8% for non-neoplastic lesions and 100% for neoplastic lesions. As per data available in our study, following statistical parameters were as follows: Sensitivity: - 85.7%, Specificity: - 100%, Positive predictive value (PPV): - 100%, Negative predictive value (NPV): - 97.7%.

Figure 1: Benign Follicular Nodule (MGG - 40X)

Figure 2: Autoimmune Thyroiditis (40X) (H&E)

Figure 3: Hashimoto's Thyroiditis: Diffuse Lymphoplasmacytic Infiltration, Lymphoid Follicles with Germinal Centers (H&E x10)

Figure 4: Papillary Carcinoma of Thyroid (40X) (H&E)

Discussion

Accurate diagnosis and management of thyroid lesions are crucial along with targeted screening and early detection strategies may be beneficial in high-risk populations.

The results of this study provide a comprehensive overview of the demographic and clinical characteristics of thyroid cases, including age, gender, lesion type, cytological and histological findings, and tumor type. Fine needle aspiration cytology (FNAC) is regarded as a gold standard in the initial diagnosis of thyroid nodules. It is simple, reliable, time saving, minimally invasive and cost effective.⁹ However there are some limitations of FNAC which a pathologist must be aware of.

The age distribution of the study shows a mean age of 41.9 years, with a range of 16 to 68 years. This is consistent with other studies by Davies L et al [10] and Kilfoy BA et al, [11] which have reported a peak incidence of thyroid cancer in the fourth to fifth decades of life. Our results are consistent with various authors Gupta et al [12] and Rangaswamy et al [13] which concluded that maximum number of thyroid lesions are seen in age group of 31-40 yrs of age group. However, Yassa et al [14] observed maximum number of cases between age group 41 and 50 years.

The gender distribution reveals a significant predominance of females, accounting for 85.7% of the cases and female to male ratio was 6:1. In other studies which were in accordance with our study Kumbhakar D et al [15] who reported female: male was 6.6:1. However Singh P et al [16] reported female: male was 4.7:1.5. It is due to fact that females are more prone for thyroid disease owing to the presence of estrogen receptors in the thyroid tissue.

In our study we find out that, distribution of lesion types shows a predominance of nodular lesions, accounting for 52.9% of the cases in our study. These findings are also consistent with previous studies that have reported nodular lesions as the most common type of thyroid lesion. In our study the cytological findings show a predominance of benign lesions, with 91.4% of the cases falling into Bethesda Category II and remaining falls in malignant category Bethesda category VI. Cibas ES, et al [17] and Nandedkar SS et al [18] also shows same findings in their research and above finding are consistent with other studies that have reported a high percentage of benign lesions in thyroid cytology.

Our results are concordant with the study done by Handa et al [19] which reported out of total 434 patients, 381 cases (87.7%) were reported to be benign, and 31 cases (7.14%) were reported to be malignant. Another study done by Swamy et al [20]

also reported that same incidence i.e. out of 120 cases of thyroid lesion 100 cases (83.66%) were benign & 20 cases (16.66%) were reported to be malignant. However in the study done by Singh P et al [16] a maximum number of cases belonged to malignant, i.e., 70 cases (57.3%) which were discordant with our study, the reason behind this may be the study was conducted on solitary nodules only.

The histological findings also show a predominance of benign lesions, with 86.3% of the cases being benign and remaining 13.7% were malignant cases. The most common finding was thyroid adenoma, with 14 cases, accounting for 27.4% of the total. This was followed by colloid goiter, present in 10 cases (19.6%), and thyroiditis, found in 8 cases (15.6%). Colloid cysts and papillary carcinoma were less prevalent, with 5 (9.8%) and 6 (11.7%) cases respectively. Multinodular goiter was identified in 7 cases, making up 13.7% of the total, while the rarest condition observed was follicular carcinoma, with only one case (1.9%).

Because it is a quick and affordable investigation, FNAC of the thyroid gland is now a well-established, most important modality and first line preoperative and pathological diagnostic test for the evaluation of diffuse thyroid lesions as well as thyroid nodules. FNAC is currently used all over the world. The use of FNAC in identifying surgical cases and offering a preoperative morphological diagnosis has greatly reduced the number of surgeries and improved the planning of appropriate surgical and other treatment protocols. Thyroid surgery has been demonstrated to have a sensitivity and diagnostic accuracy of up to 85–95% in skilled hands.

Our study shows that the FNAC has the sensitivity, specificity, positive predictive value and negative predictive value 85.7%, 100%, 100% and 97.7%. Same results were also find out by Geetanjali G et al [21], with a positive predictive value of 89–98%, a negative predictive value of 94–99%, and false negative rates as low as 5–10% and also comparable to the study done by Afroze et al [22] where malignancy showed sensitivity of 61.90%, specificity of 99.31%, positive predictive value of 92.86%, and negative predictive value of 94.74%.

The data in the present study, indicates that the prognosis of thyroid diseases is logically related to the introduction of the new, simplified Bethesda thyroid reporting system into six categories, which may also improve diagnostic reproducibility. The specific cancer risks associated with each diagnostic category provide direction for patient management. This study's findings have significant clinical implications. The high prevalence of

benign thyroid lesions underscores the importance of accurate diagnosis and management. Cytology and histology are crucial tools in differentiating between benign and malignant lesions, with a higher incidence of thyroid cancer observed in females and older individuals, highlighting the need for targeted screening. As thyroid lesions become more common, diagnostic challenges often arise in distinguishing between various thyroid conditions. Fine needle aspiration cytology (FNAC), recognized as the gold standard, is vital for initial evaluation, helping to avoid unnecessary surgeries. In tertiary hospitals, FNAC should be the primary diagnostic approach, supplemented by thyroid function tests and antibody levels to determine the appropriate treatment path.

Limitations of the Study:

The study has some limitations. The sample size is relatively small, which may limit the generalizability of the findings. The study is also limited to a single institution, which may not be representative of the broader population. Future studies with larger sample sizes and multiple institutions are needed to confirm the findings of this study.

Conclusion

Cytological and histological evaluations are highlighted as essential tools in distinguishing between benign and malignant lesions. While the study acknowledges limitations such as a small sample size and single-institution design, its comprehensive data collection and analysis provide a strong foundation for understanding thyroid cases. The conclusions align with previous research, reinforcing the study's validity and generalizability. The findings have important implications for clinical practice and future research, emphasizing the need for further investigation into thyroid demographics and the development of more effective diagnostic and therapeutic strategies.

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